

Does buying local help? Consequences of poorly-regulated short food supply chains

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Abstract

Local food production offers a way to reduce the environmental impacts (carbon emissions) generated by the supply of food. This paper describes research into the distances farmers travel and their related carbon emissions for different direct marketing channels. The results are based on a survey of 149 Hungarian farmers in 2013 in three differently-regulated types of markets. In contrast to a priori expectations, food mileage is the highest for produce sold at farmers' markets - which have increasingly been promoted as a means of fostering localism. Due to the lack of appropriate regulation and economies of scale, (socio)-economic and environmental goals are coming into conflict as larger enterprises transport their products further (or more often). The case study findings offer a message at a general level: they indicate the need for optimal regulation of local food systems, otherwise the purchasing of poorly-informed environmentally conscious consumers might create unintended impacts.

Keywords: local food; farmers' market; linear mixed effects model; carbon emission; Hungary

1 Introduction

Agriculture is responsible for more than 13% of global anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, mostly as a consequence of soil and livestock management, rice production, and biomass burning (IPCC, 2007). Moreover, agriculture is a major driver of indirect emissions through land use change (mostly deforestation) and the transportation of agricultural products along the supply chain (Burney et al., 2010; Freibauer, 2003; Niggli et al., 2009). The concept of ‘food miles’ and opportunities for reducing carbon footprints via direct purchasing from farmer-vendors in short food supply chains (SFSCs) are often detailed in grey literature that concerns local food systems, although there appears to be no consensus in academic literature about the benefits of these approaches. Locality is a key concept; however, conceptualization of the term “local” is highly variable. As a consequence, “acceptable” food mileage and footprints depend on the cultural and regional context: analyses of consumer perceptions and policy documents suggest that food that is sourced anywhere from distances of 30 km to 644 km may be considered ‘local’ (The US Food Conservation and Energy Act of 2008) (Edwards-Jones, 2010; Pirog and Rasmussen, 2008). Brown (2002) summarizes in his review that the average travelling distance is around 32 km with a considerable amount of variability: some farmers may travel up to 400 km to bring their products to market. Full-time growers are liable to travel twice as much further than part-time growers (Gale, 1997). As from the consumers’ side, consumers definitely show an increased willingness to pay for local food (Feldmann and Hamm, 2015; Gracia et al., 2012; Grebitus et al., 2013), although recent contributions imply that their willingness might depend on the type of marketing channel (Printezis and Grebitus, 2018). Even the impacts of the most stringently-regulated SFSCs (compared to conventional global sales channels) in terms of environmental consequences remain controversial. Depending on the local geographical-climatic context, delivery of produce through conventional food supply and global trading chains can have less environmental impact than when food is locally produced - for example, when the regional growing season is short (Carlsson-Kanyama, 1998; Smith et al., 2005), or when there is a need for long-term storage and cooling (Jones, 2002; Saunders and Barber, 2007). Furthermore, transport contributes to overall emissions throughout the product life-cycle to only a minor extent (10-20%) (Cuéllar and Webber, 2010; Weber and Matthews, 2008), whereas production, or structural problems of the supply chain resulting in losses and wastage has a much higher carbon impact (Benis and Ferrão, 2017). Conventional channels often utilise very efficient logistics that create less overall emissions compared to the often inefficient chains that exist between countless individual consumers and producers (Coley et al., 2009; Smith et al., 2016). However, SFSC farmers can cooperate in order to increase their efficiency and profitability, with

associated environmental improvements (Andersson et al., 2005) that bring their performance into line with that of conventional agri-food value chains (Mundler and Rumpus, 2012) in terms of carbon footprints. Although a growing body of literature exists that has sought to provide a comparative analysis of the environmental impacts of conventional and short food supply chains, much less attention has been paid to the differences between different SFSC marketing channels. The aim of the authors of this paper is to provide information and analysis about the travelling distances of farmers and their related carbon footprints for different direct marketing channels in Hungary, where three different types of market are present due to the existence of highly specialized regulations. Results are discussed in the light of the environmental expectations of decision-makers that are connected to the development of local food systems. Factors that may be important in shaping farmers' decisions about the distances they travel are also described.

1.1 The local Hungarian context

Many SFSC marketing channels (such as on-farm sales, pick-your-own, etc.) are employed in Hungary, but market selling is by far the most profitable method of trading products for farmers (Juhász, 2012). Presently, three different types of market can be distinguished in Hungary based on regulations and some other characteristics Benedek et al. (2018). At conventional markets (CMs) the presence of retailers is typical, though a smaller sales area is usually dedicated to farmer-vendors too. These public markets are characterized by having permanent facilities and infrastructure (e.g. they are typically paved and covered) and are maintained by local authorities. Typically, there is a long-term (usually one year) rental contract between the CM and the farmer-vendor which ensures the farmer the right to rent a specified table for the contractual price. Another type of market is legally defined (Act CLXIV of 2005 on Trade) as a farmers' market (FM). In line with the aspirations of the European Union (Kneafsey et al., 2013), SFSCs are being promoted in Hungary due to considerations of rural development, with attendant environmental benefits expected as a consequence of the increased emphasis on localism. Specific political support for FMs is important for their establishment. Farmers may sell their own (personally-grown) produce at a FM so long as it is grown within a 40 km radius of the point of sale. All the produce that originates from within a single county may also be regarded as local, while any farmer is allowed to sell produce at a FM in the capital, Budapest. Farmers' markets are usually organized by non-governmental actors and are characterized by their temporary (portable) facilities. They are typically located at or in school gardens, church yards, community buildings, etc. Instead of engaging in long-term rental agreements, vendors pay a daily entrance fee. The legislation (Ministerial Decree (FVM) No. 52/2010. (IV. 30.) amended by Ministerial Decree (VM) No. 4/2010. (VII.5.)), which makes the opening of

farmers' markets easier, came into force in 2012. Since then, the number of farmers' markets in Hungary has constantly increased; most of them can now be found in Central Hungary, especially in Budapest (Juhász, 2012) due to the higher purchasing power of that area. As the emphasis at farmers' market is put on locality, direct interactions and originality, prices are usually higher (Buller and Morris, 2003; Kirwan, 2006) than at conventional markets (Benedek et al., 2018). This may entice farmers to sell their produce at FMs rather than at CMs, although the still-low number of FMs may be a limiting factor. Accordingly, it is more likely that the distance that a farmer is willing to travel to sell at a FM is greater. An organic market (OM) is the third type of legally-defined market. For this type of market no geographical limitations exist concerning the provenance of products, but organic certification is required. There are fewer OMs than farmers' markets, and prices are typically even higher (Benedek et al., 2018).

2 Material and methods

2.1 Survey design

Face-to-face surveys were conducted among 149 Hungarian farmer-vendors in 2013 (April to June). In total, 20 conventional, organic and farmers' markets were visited in the capital Budapest (BP) with a population of 1.7 million, Debrecen (D) the second biggest city and capital of Hajdú-Bihar County (a NUTS 3 region) of 207 000 inhabitants, and Tura (T), a small town of 8 000 inhabitants in Pest County. The single market of Tura was included, as, although there is no similar outlet in the little town for farmers to choose to sell at, they may decide to transport their produce directly to Budapest, which is approximately 50 km away. All the markets included in the research are held at least weekly, and many of them (especially the conventional markets) are open daily. There are no official data available about such markets; to the best of our knowledge all the markets in Tura and Debrecen were involved, and an estimated 20% of the markets in Budapest. As for organic markets, their proportion in the BP sample corresponds to their estimated proportion of markets in Budapest (8%). The smaller but wealthier part of Budapest (Buda) has approximately 35% of the capital's purchasing power (based on 2013 data). This corresponds to the proportion of the Buda-based CMs and FMs in our sample. Another factor included in market selection was the need to involve all the possible market opening-time variants (e.g. some markets are open six days per week, some only on one day during the week, or on the weekend). Further selection of markets was done randomly. Additionally, individual farmer-vendors were randomly selected for interview. The questionnaire contained three major sections (for a description of the key variables see Table 1). The first part was designed to collect data about the socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers (age,

education). The second part focused on farmer-related production and marketing-specific characteristics, such as location (at a settlement level), area, product diversity, use of organic methods, use of storage facilities, etc. Finally, the farmer's motivation for selling at a specific market was examined. First, the distance by road between the farm and the market place at which the survey was conducted was calculated using the website <http://www.viamichelin.com/> (selecting the option "Avoid tolls"). If the farm was located in Budapest, the district was identified to allow more accurate estimation of distances. If the farm was located within the city/settlement (in the case of Debrecen and Tura), the distance was taken to be 10 km or 5 km, respectively. To calculate the travelling-related CO₂ emissions, data about the number of market days and the type of vehicle used by the farmers were incorporated, and weekly emissions were calculated for each respondent (using the size of agricultural area used for production). To calculate the CO₂ emissions of each major vehicle type data from the UK government's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) were used. According to the latest available, comparable data (ANFAC, 2013; CSO, 2014), the average age of vehicles in use in Hungary is five years more than in the UK (11.9 and 7.24 years in 2011, respectively), thus the 2008 DEFRA conversion factors were applied to our 2013 vehicle type data. The proportions of petrol and diesel vehicles were also accounted for.

2.2 Linear mixed effects models

To analyse the relationship between the distance from market and other explanatory variables that might play a role, linear mixed effects (LME) models were used. The variability in distance between different types of market (CM, FM, OM) and regions (BP, D, T) was first examined using simple descriptive statistics and coefficients of variation. Mixed models, compared to simple linear regression models, incorporate fixed and random effects and thereby permit the modelling of unbalanced or correlated data. By using LMEs it is possible to model the variability in data that stems from spatial, temporal, spatiotemporal or other sources of grouped structuring in data that lead to correlations in a sample. In the present case, the variation in distance caused by the hierarchical structure of the data (where several observations came from different regions and within regions from different types of market, thereby creating a complex structure of associations) was accounted for. The use of LMEs makes possible the partition of the overall variation of the dependent variable into components corresponding to different levels of data hierarchy (Gałeczki and Burzykowski, 2013). First, three separate models were fitted to the data. These accounted for the variance due to the different legal environment in different regions and types of markets as random effects (i.e. FMs were exempted from the maximum-of-40 km distance specification in the case of Budapest, while there was no geographical limitation for

CMs and OMs). The two most widely-used linear mixed effect models (random intercept and random intercept and slope models) are now described in more detail. The random intercept (RI) model is described as follows: $Dist_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_n x_n + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$, where $Dist_{ij}$ represents the observed distance of the farm of farmer i from the market in a region (Budapest, Debrecen, Tura) and type of market (conventional, farmers' and organic market) j , and $x_1 : x_n$ are the fixed effects (see Table 1). In the case of a random intercept model the residual of a usual linear regression model is partitioned into a subject-specific random intercept component u_i ($u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2)$) and a residual ε_{ij} ($\varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$), while u_i and ε_{ij} are orthogonal. The random intercept model implies that the total variance is $Var(Dist_{ij}) = \sigma_u^2 + \sigma^2$. In other words, the total residual variance is divided into a between-subject component (σ_u^2), and a within-subject component (σ^2) (Hothorn and Everitt, 2009).

The random intercept and slope (RI/RS) model contains two types of random effects: the first one (u_i) models the heterogeneity in intercepts, and the second one (ν_i) models heterogeneity in effects (slopes). In other words, ν_i captures the subject-specific differences of the effect of area on distance by market type in different regions:

$Dist_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Area + \beta_2 x_2 \dots + \beta_n x_n + u_i + \nu_i Area_j + \varepsilon_{ij}$, where the two random effects are assumed to have a bivariate normal distribution with zero mean and variances, σ_u^2 and σ_ν^2 . The total variance of this model can be calculated as $Var(Dist_{ij}) = \sigma_u^2 + 2\sigma_{u\nu} Area_j + \sigma_\nu^2 Area_j^2 + \sigma^2$ (Hothorn and Everitt, 2009).

The third type of model tested is a random slope only (RS) model that accounts only for the different effects of the size of area farmed on the distances from different types of market in the three regions. It is not described more in detail here. The model comparison statistics are shown in Table S1 in the Supplementary Information. In the case of unbalanced data the classical statistical approaches for significance testing are not appropriate so a Likelihood Ratio Test was applied to define the significance of the fixed effects through model comparisons. The Likelihood Ratio Test compares the likelihood of two models with each other. By keeping the random effects structure constant in the process of comparison, the full model (which contains the random effects and all fixed effects) is compared against reduced models where the fixed effect in question is excluded. This approach allows the testing of whether, with a specific fixed effect, the full model is significantly different from the reduced model (where this fixed effect is excluded). The quality of the model fit was analysed with an R^2 statistic, as suggested by Xu (2003). The coefficient of determination for the whole model is calculated as $1 - (\text{residual variance of the model} / \text{raw variance of the data})$; and explained variation due to the fixed effects is calculated as $1 - (\text{residual variance of model with fixed effects} / \text{residual variance of model without the fixed effects})$ (Xu, 2003). All analyses were carried out using R software (R Core

Team, 2018). Package lme4 provided functions for mixed effects modelling (Bates et al., 2015).

3 Results and discussion

Most farmers are involved in horticulture (77%); the share for animal husbandry farmers is 17%, while mixed farm farmers constitute the rest of the sample (6%). Table 1 contains the descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the sample

Variable	Description	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Age	Continuous	149	54.71	13.98	26	85
Education	Categorical ^a	149	2.35	1.26	1	5
Area	Continuous, hectare	144	12.77	46.90	0	367
Transport (Private vehicle)	Binary (1=car, truck, 0=public transport)	149	0.89	0.31	0	1
Organic	Binary (1=organic production methods ² , 0=conventional)	148	0.18	0.39	0	1
Greenhouse	Continuous, hectare	147	0.06	0.22	0	2.5
Long-term contract	Binary (1=yes, 0=no contract)	149	0.70	0.46	0	1
Specialized storage facility	Binary (1= air conditioned, 0=other or none)	149	0.53	0.50	0	1
Income from agricultural activity	Percentage	130	65.93	37.63	0	100
Income from processed product	Percentage	145	21.58	36.00	0	100
Number of product	Categorical	146	22.19	34.45	1	350
Market days per week	Categorical	148	3.11	1.93	1	14
Motivation – Closeness	Binary (1=yes, 0=no)	149	0.07	0.25	0	1
Motivation – Monetary	Binary (1=yes, 0=no)	148	0.43	0.50	0	1
Motivation – Emotional	Binary (1=yes, 0=no)	149	0.61	0.49	0	1

Notes: a: Education is measured on a scale of five: 1: primary education (8 years' schooling); 2: secondary education (12 years' schooling); 3: secondary education, with specialisation in agriculture; 4: higher education; 5: higher education, with specialisation in agriculture. 2: The farmer was asked if they used organic farming methods but not to specify which method nor supply proof of organic certification.

Similarly to previous findings (Brown, 2002; Juhász, 2012; Kneafsey et al., 2013), market vendors are revealed to typically be middle age. Farm size is around 13 hectares on average, which is in line with expectations (Juhász, 2012; Lass et al., 2003; Meert et al., 2005). Four farmers in the sample operate on more than 60 hectares; these individuals are all involved in animal husbandry or run mixed farms. These (organic) farmers also sell an exceptionally high number of products.

The high count number of products may arise due to the data collection method which was assessed in a way as to reflect consumer considerations: different varieties of the same species or processed products that contained different species alongside a basic ingredient were regarded as being different. Similarly, market days per week can exceed seven due to the method of assessment: if a farmer's family members visited other markets on the same day this was counted as an additional market day/s. 43% of farmers report to having some kind of monetary motivation for visiting a specific market (while 61% mention emotional considerations). Several authors (Bakucs et al., 2012; Juhász, 2012; Kneafsey et al., 2013) have reported that participation in SFSCs is motivated by the desire to make greater profit. Thus, it is possible that the lower reported incidence here is the result of social desirability bias (Grimm, 2010); i.e. farmers tend to place emphasis on 'respectable' reasons for participating, such as enjoying the good atmosphere of the market, instead of on their financial status and monetary expectations. Figure 1 shows the travelling distances, area size and CO₂ emissions by conventional, farmers' and organic markets in Budapest, Debrecen and Tura. Numerical values (descriptive statistics) are displayed in Table S2 and Table S3 in the Supplementary Information.

Travelling distances in the case of farmers' markets is substantially higher than that for conventional markets, a finding which is not in line with the putative notion of the environmentally friendliness of local food systems. The greater distances travelled to farmers' markets than to those located in the countryside (outside Budapest) can however be explained by the lack of regulation concerning this feature. Whereas produce may be transported a maximum distance of 40 km to FMs in the countryside (the average distance for travel to FM in Debrecen was less than 40 km; only in 2 cases was this limit exceeded), FMs located in the capital are not similarly restricted. Focusing on the travelling distance to organic markets, the patterns are completely different in Budapest and in Debrecen. Farmers travel furthest to organic markets in Budapest (similar to the situation with FMs), while in Debrecen the case appears to be more similar to that with travelling to CMs. Spearman's rank correlation indicates that there is a significant and strong relationship between distance from market and farm size in the case of organic farms ($r=0.675$; $p=0.008$). This implies the presence of the economies of scale: the more produce there is, the more it is worth farmers' travelling in order to supply greater consumer demand. Searching for the highest possible revenue is necessary otherwise the profitability of organic farming over conventional practices easily becomes questionable (Uematsu and Mishra, 2012). Figure 1c depicts the weekly carbon emission for distances projected onto the agricultural area used for production (numerical findings are summarized in Table S3). Weekly carbon emissions per hectare for farmers who transport products to organic market in Budapest are significantly lower than those of the other two

Figure 1: Distance travelled, area and CO₂ emission. 1a: Travelling distance by type of market in the different regions. 1b: Area farmed by type of market and region. 1c: CO₂ emission based on distances projected onto the size of agricultural area used for production. BP: Budapest; D: Debrecen; T: Tura

market types, which is due to the fewer market days. Table 2 shows the coefficients of variation by different region and type of market.

Table 2: Coefficient of variation for distance

	Budapest	Debrecen	Tura	Total
CM	0.94	0.57	0.86	1.26
FM	0.73	0.56	-	0.78
OM	0.59	0.16	-	0.90
Total	0.90	0.82	0.86	1.16

The findings indicate that there is great overall variability across markets and regions and thus the use of linear fixed effects models is justified. As could be expected a priori, the variability in distance is less in regions in which produce transportation distances are regulated than in Budapest. In order to investigate what factors influence farmers' decision-making about travelling distances, three models were tested on the sample; a random intercept (RI), a random slope (RS) and a random intercept and slope (RI/RS) model. Results of the model comparison are presented in Table S1. AIC and BIC criteria and the Chi-square test show that the RI/RS model does better than the random slope only model, but results are not significantly different from the RI-only model. The results of the random intercept model are presented below. Table 3 shows the estimates and the corresponding p-values of likelihood ratio tests for the fixed effects. The overall amount of variance explained by the model is 59%, while 24% of variance can be explained by the fixed effects. The size of the agricultural area from which the products derive positively affects the distance they are taken to market (mainly because of the data from Budapest, where, as previously explained, there is no specified limit to which produce may be transported). Similarly, farmers who use greenhouses for production and air-conditioned facilities for storing also travel greater distances. Both the proportion of income derived from agricultural activity, and the income from processed products have a significant effect, but the sign is different. Farmers whose income is less dependent on farming have a lower willingness to travel, a finding which is line with that of Gale (1997). As the proportion of income derived from processed products is higher, farmers who sell processed items are more likely to travel further. The variables are all related to the size (development, diversification) of the farms, which implies the effect of economies of scale: farmers from larger enterprises are willing to travel further in search of suitable outlets for their goods. This finding is supported by the impact of personal motivation. Although this mostly plays a marginal role in explaining the distances travelled to market, financial motivation do have a significant positive effect. The negative sign for organic production (as a measure of diversification and development of the farms) seems to contradict the earlier statement at first sight. However, as demonstrated above,

Table 3: Random intercept model for the sample

Fixed effects	Estimate	Std. Error	Likelihood Ratio test	p-value
(Intercept)	59.81	27.41		
Years of experience	-0.475	0.286	2.708	0.010
Education	5.098	3.581	2.007	0.157
Area	0.144	0.097	33.88	< 0.001
Private vehicle	-19.62	13.74	2.018	0.156
Organic	-15.09	13.72	10.25	0.001
Greenhouse	29.73	15.95	12.58	< 0.001
Long-term contract	-0.895	11.12	0.006	0.938
Specialized storage facility	13.76	7.792	3.062	0.080
Income from agricultural activity	-0.071	0.123	196.8	< 0.001
Income from processed product	0.110	0.124	30.52	< 0.001
Number of products	-0.243	0.145	11.76	< 0.001
Market days	-1.756	2.138	20.38	< 0.001
Motivation – Closeness	8.661	16.02	0.292	0.589
Motivation – Monetary	11.66	11.01	22.48	< 0.001
Motivation – Emotional	7.150	10.69	0.446	0.504
Random effects	Variance	Std. Dev.		
Region: Type of Market	2732	52.27		
Residual	1373	37.05		
Variance explained		59%		
Variance explained by fixed effects		24%		
Number of obs: 117, groups: 7				

willingness to travel is heterogeneous among organic farmers (see Fig. 1) and is strongly influenced by the size of area farmed. Farm size may also be connected to the number of products (another important measure of size and diversification) which also affects willingness to travel. However, organic farmers tend to sell many more products (Benedek et al., 2018), which might explain the overall negative effect. The negative effect of the number of market days may clearly be explained in reference to the increasing cost of travelling on multiple occasions.

4 Conclusions

The difference in the distances Hungarian farmers are willing to travel to different types of market is unexpected. Results show that respondents with bigger and more developed farms are willing to travel further and/or more often, a fact which may undermine the pro-environmental initiatives of decision-makers. In spite of strict geographical limitations which were introduced to promote local food, both food mileage and CO₂ emissions appear to be significantly higher for FMs compared to conventional and organic markets. This pattern is strengthened by the fact that farmers' markets in Budapest are exempted from complying with the maximum distance regulation that is in effect elsewhere in Hungary (which is designed to allow farmers an equal

chance to sell their products on the market in a region with the greatest national purchasing power). Two conflicting policy goals are thus in evidence; one is to reduce the environmental impact of food supply while the other is to support the socio-economic wellbeing of farmers. One potential solution for harmonizing these two distinct policy goals is the promotion of cooperative ventures (see Andersson et al. (2005)) such as joint marketing. However, due to the low level of cooperation among Hungarian farmers (Bakucs et al., 2012), clear political support and related motivational measures would be needed to ensure broader participation. Moreover, in order to verify the origin of a certain product in a local food system, more accurate guidance on increasing traceability is needed. This analysis draws attention to the importance of improving the accuracy of the planning and management of local food systems. Consumers usually associate farmers' markets and organic markets with better environmental performance (Kneafsey et al., 2013). However, a lack of appropriate regulation may produce unintended impacts due to conflicting environmental and socio-economic tendencies. A lack of understanding about the environmental impacts of making purchases at different types of markets may reduce the efficiency of the environmental efforts of consumers and thereby also limit the efficiency of environmental policies.

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Supplementary Information

Table S1: Model comparison

	Df	AIC	BIC	LL	Dev.	Chi2	Chi Df	Pr(>Chi2)
RI (1 Region: Type of market)	18	1237.8	1287.50	-600.90	1201.80	4.78	2	0.09
RS (0+Area Region: Type of market)	18	1260.5	1310.30	-612.27	1224.50	27.53	2	< 0.001
RI/RS (Area Region: Type of market)	20	1237.0	1292.20	-598.50	1197.00			

Table S2: Descriptive statistics – distance travelled (km)

Region Type of market	Budapest			Debrecen			Tura
	CM	FM	OM	CM	FM	OM	CM
N	47	34	10	23	11	4	20
Average	49.9	72.8	148.2	14.3	37.9	9.3	8.1
SD	43.4	49.8	86.8	6.8	15.5	1.5	7
Variance	2013	2635	7529	49.4	353.1	2.3	48.3
Minimum	15.7	10	18	10	24	7	5
Maximum	280	208	247	35	71	10	31
Median	43	61	151	11	31	10	5

Table S3: Weekly CO₂ emission by type of market (g/ha)

Region Type of market	Budapest			Debrecen			Tura
	CM	FM	OM	CM	FM	OM	CM
N	46	31	10	22	10	4	20
Average	42005	76517	11 690	39 685	52 805	8 907	19 456
SD	50363	103202	13141	49056	95540	6468	13783
Min	1148	64	236	3005	492	532	5 641
Max	221260	356475	40374	204871	311696	14341	51218